

tipologiyasi bo'yicha turli tamoyil va tasniflarning taklif etilishi davom etmoqda. Chunonchi, obrazning asardagi vazifasi, ya'ni funksiyasidan kelib chiqib uni tiplarga bo'lish masalasi ham qizg'in bahslarga sabab bo'lgan. Funksiyasiga ko'ra obrazlar asosiy(kardinal) va yordamchi (katatizator) obrazlarga bo'linishi haqidagi fikr R.Bart, V.Propp asarlarida ilgari surilgan. Sv. Todorov esa qahramonlarni ular orasidagi hissiy-emotsional rishtalar va munosabatga ko'ra tasniflashni yoqlaydi [4.]. Ko'rinadiki, badiiy obraz tipologiyasining turli aspektda o'rganilishi poetikaning muhim masalalaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

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CATEGORIES OF CHARACTERS IN LITERATURE AND THEIR INTERPRETATION

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Annotation. This article gives important information about characters in the novel as characters play the key role and all events happen around them. Indeed, writer's description of different characters often shows up clearly in his/her writing, and

readers have the job of identifying writer's purpose. For this reason it is crucial to know categories of characters and their classification in literature.

Key words: character, categories of characters, protagonists, antagonists, round, flat, foil, static or dynamic.

Although readers usually consider plot the central element of fiction, writers usually remark that stories begin with characters. They imagine a person in loving detail and then wait to see what that character will do. In literature, characters are the driving forces behind a story. They are responsible for creating and resolving problems, and their personalities are crucial in developing the themes of a work. There are several categories of characters that are commonly found in literature, each with its unique interpretation.

Protagonist: A protagonist is the central character of a story who faces and manages problems directly. They are typically the one who takes action to resolve problems and drive the story forward.

Antagonist: An antagonist represents the opposition to the protagonist's goals and desires. They create a conflict that the protagonist must overcome to succeed in their quest [1; 78].

Foil: A foil character is one who is opposite in personality or behavior to the protagonist. These characters help the reader gain further insight into the protagonist and their actions.

Round character: A round character is one who has depth and complexity, with multi-dimensional personalities, motivations, and emotions.

Flat character: A flat character is one who lacks depth and is typically a stereotype or caricature of a certain group or personality type.

Dynamic character: A dynamic character goes through a significant change over the course of the story. This change can be either external or internal and is typically the result of a conflict or challenge presented in the plot.

Understanding the roles and personalities of various characters in literature can enhance our appreciation of the story and its themes. Each of these categories of

characters provides a unique insight into the human experience and the challenges we all face [4; 72].

Expanding on the categories of characters in literature, it is worth noting that characters can exist in multiple categories. For example, a character can be both a protagonist and a dynamic character if they drive the story forward and undergo significant personal growth. Additionally, characters can evolve over the course of the story, moving from one category to another. For instance, a foil character can become a dynamic character if they undergo a significant change. It is also worth mentioning minor characters who play important roles in driving the plot forward or symbolizing a theme. Although they may not fit neatly into these categories, they are vital to a well-rounded story. Ultimately, the different categories of characters provide an excellent tool to understand the complexity of human nature and the way it is manifested through storytelling.

Literary characters can be categorized as protagonists, antagonists, round, flat, static or dynamic. Protagonists are typically good, and the story revolves around them, while antagonists typically oppose the protagonist and are viewed as evil. Round characters are more complex and undergo character development, while flat characters are one-dimensional and play minor roles. Static characters do not change their actions throughout the story, while dynamic characters undergo a significant change. Understanding these categories helps readers grasp the story's overall message. Literature often categorizes characters into various types, each representing a particular archetype. These categories can be useful in analyzing character traits and understanding their roles in a story.

One such category is the hero, typically portrayed as a courageous and virtuous character who embarks on a journey of self-discovery or a mission to save others. They inspire and uplift readers or viewers with their determination and sense of justice. Another category is the villain, the antagonist who opposes the hero, often embodying negative traits such as greed, jealousy or cruelty. They are the source of conflict in the story and drive the plot forward.

There are also characters who fall under the category of the mentor, providing guidance and wisdom to the hero [5;25]. They are often older and experienced, offering valuable advice that helps the protagonist grow and develop over time. The sidekick is another character archetype, often serving as a loyal friend or companion to the hero. They may not always be as heroic or significant as the protagonist, but they bring something unique and valuable to the story. Finally, love interests are characters whose role is to offer affection and romantic tension to the plot, becoming a major driving force for the protagonist's actions and emotions. In well plotted story, nothing is irrelevant; everything is related. The first approach would describe narrative structure in a purely episode-based and plot-driven manner, while the second approach additionally incorporates the psychology and experientiality of characters.

Analyzing and interpreting these character categories can help us gain a deeper understanding of the story and its underlying themes. As we explore the motivations and actions of each character, we can gain valuable insights into human nature and the complexity of the world around us.

Understanding literary character is a dynamic process in which the reader's knowledge structures and cognitive and emotional strategies continually interact with textual information [6; 6]. Dynamic effects of reading, such as inference or the formation and rejection of hypotheses, can only be described adequately if this interplay between top-down and bottom-up processing of information is examined. From these two sources of information, readers construct mental models not only of fictional situations, time, and space, but also of characters. Throughout the reading process, readers elaborate, modify, or revise character models to incorporate incoming information. A cognitive theory of literary character not only provides a systematic account of the constituent elements of character-reception from both text-related and reader-related sources, but it also proposes a process model that tries to capture the most important distinctive phases of mental-model construction in character-reception. The cognitive approach offers new categories for the analysis of literary character.

One can conclude that, literary characters can be categorized as protagonists, antagonists, round, flat, static or dynamic. This classification plays a significant role in shaping the reader's perception of the story's message. Understanding these categories helps readers grasp the story's overall message.

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ADABIYOT VA ADABIY ALOQALARNI DAVRLASHTITISH MASALALARI

Karayev Umed Jo'rayevich,

Surxondaryo viloyati Surxondaryo viloyati pedagoglarni yangi metodikalarga o'rgatish milliy markazi "Tillarni o'qitish metodikasi" kafedrası katta o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va fors-tojik adabiy aloqalarini davrlashtitish masalalari haqida mulohaza yuritiladi. Tadqiqotlarda asosan Hirot adabiy muhitidagi hamkorliklarga e'tibor qaratilgan. Ammo ilmiy kuzatishlar